

Mean Time to Unsafe Failure for Markov, Semi-Markov, and Globally Time Dependent Models¹²

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Abstract—With the increased use of automatic equipment, electronics, and networks comes a concern about their failure modes. If they fail it is desirable that they fail in a benign manner. Hence, a reliability parameter of interest is the mean time to unsafe failure. The models and methods for computing this mean, however, are still in an early stage. This paper presents new material that permits examining more complex and realistic models.

relevant parameter is the mean (or expected) time to an unsafe failure—mttuf.

This topic is new with a previous publication being [1] which considers just Markov models. This paper differs in four respects from [1]. It takes a simpler approach to computing Markov models. It includes the repair process in the computation. It uses a symbol manipulation program (The MATLAB Symbolic Math Toolbox) that permits handling larger and more realistic models. It derives a formula for mttuf from the single cycle parameters and applies this formula to semi-Markov and globally time dependent models.

One feature of mttuf computations is that the results are opposite of what we expect, even for the simple Markov models. Increasing redundancy decreases the mttuf. Increasing the component failure rate increases the mttuf. These issues still remain to be resolved. Perhaps continued investigation using even more realistic models will solve these problems

Section two presents the method for computing the mttuf for Markov models. Section three derives the formula for mttuf in terms of single cycle parameters. Sections four and five consider semi-Markov and globally time dependent models.

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1. INTRODUCTION

If a large number of components operate for a long period of time, then there will almost certainly be failures. It is then important that the system fail in a safe manner. The meaning of safe depends on the circumstances. If it is a traffic control system, then safe means rerouting traffic or bringing traffic to a safe stop. For a controller, it can mean passing control to a backup system. For the internet it can mean rerouting the flow of data, not losing any data, or having a short downtime. For all such systems, a

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2. MARKOV MODELS

Mean time to unsafe failure for Markov models can be handled by the Laplace transform since the limit of the derivative of the Laplace transform equals the negative of the first moment. Suppose $f(t)$ is the density function for the time to unsafe failure. The Laplace transform derivations are

$$L[f(t)] = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt$$

$$\frac{d(L[f(t)])}{ds} = \int_0^{\infty} -t e^{-st} f(t) dt \quad (1)$$

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{d(L[f(t)])}{ds} = - \int_0^{\infty} t f(t) dt$$

The Laplace transform can be obtained from the Chapman-Kolmogorov differential equations [2,3]. Get the transform of each equation, then solve a set of linear algebraic equations.

Example: Threplex with Coverage

A universal concept in reliability is that of coverage—the probability of a good outcome given a failure [4,5]. One of the easiest ways to include coverage in a model is to multiply by a coverage factor (usually denoted by C), but this method has some limitations which are discussed in the next subsection. Consider a threplex where the good outcome is a safe failure upon the failure of a component. The model, using a coverage factor, is given in figure 1. The component failure rate is λ ; the coverage factor is C; the repair rate is ϵ . In state 2 the system has failed safe upon the first component failure, and the system continues to operate. In state 3 the system fails safe upon the second component failure, and the system shuts down until repair. State 4 is fail unsafe.

Figure 1: Threplex with Coverage

The Chapman-Kolmogorov differential equations are

$$p_1'(t) = -3\lambda p_1(t) + \epsilon p_3(t)$$

$$p_2'(t) = 3\lambda C p_1(t) - 2\lambda p_2(t)$$

$$p_3'(t) = 2\lambda C p_2(t) - \epsilon p_3(t) \quad (2)$$

$$p_4'(t) = 3\lambda(1-C)p_1(t) + 2\lambda(1-C)p_2(t)$$

Given the system begins in state 1, the Laplace transforms of the Chapman-Kolmogorov equations are

$$sP_1 - 1 = -3\lambda P_1 + \epsilon P_3$$

$$sP_2 = 3\lambda C P_1 - 2\lambda P_2$$

$$sP_3 = 2\lambda C P_2 - \epsilon P_3 \quad (3)$$

$$sP_4 = 3\lambda(1-C)P_1 + 2\lambda(1-C)P_2$$

where capital P_i is the Laplace transform of $p_i(t)$. Solving for sP_4 yields

$$sP_4 = \frac{\lambda [2\lambda C^2 s - 2\lambda s + 2\epsilon \lambda C^2 - \epsilon s - s^2 + \epsilon C s - 2\lambda \epsilon + C s^2]}{[6\lambda^2 \epsilon C^2 - 6\lambda^2 \epsilon - 5\lambda \epsilon s - 6\lambda^2 s - 5\lambda s^2 - \epsilon s^2 - s]} \quad (4)$$

The step above is a point in the derivation where it is easy to solve for the wrong quantity. By the derivations in (1) we want the Laplace transform of the density function, which is sP_4 , not the transform of the distribution function, which is P_4 .

Taking the negative of the derivative of sP_4 and substituting $s=0$ gives

$$- \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} [sP_4]' = -3 \frac{\lambda (2\lambda C^2 - 2\lambda - \epsilon - C\epsilon)}{(6\lambda^2 \epsilon C^2 - 6\lambda^2 \epsilon)} + 3 \frac{\lambda (2\lambda \epsilon C^2 - 2\lambda \epsilon) (-6\lambda^2 - 5\lambda \epsilon)}{(6\lambda^2 \epsilon C^2 - 6\lambda^2 \epsilon)^2} \quad (5)$$

Suppose the parameter values are
 failure rate $\lambda = 1e-4/\text{hour}$
 repair rate $\epsilon = 1/(24 \text{ hours})$
 coverage $C = 0.9999$.

Substitution gives $mttuf = 4.1786 e+7$ hours.

Example: Fourplex with Coverage

Suppose we have a threeplex with a design flaw. With probability P_F the system fails whenever a single component fails. The model for a threeplex with a design flaw is given in figure 2.

Figure 2: Threeplex with Design Flaw

Figure 2 is identical to figure 1 with $C = 1 - P_F$. Hence, using a coverage factor is equivalent to assuming a design flaw—the design is adequate for recovery from some, but not all, failures. A general principle is that redundancy does not overcome design flaws. In fact, redundancy can make matters worse. Consider a fourplex with a coverage whose model is given in figure 3.

Figure 3: Fourplex with Coverage

With the same parameters as for the threeplex
 failure rate $\lambda = 1e-4/\text{hour}$
 repair rate $\epsilon = 1/(24 \text{ hours}) =$
 coverage $C = 0.9999$.

The $mttuf = 3.6190 e+7$ hours, which is less than the $mttuf$ for the threeplex.

Threeplex and Fourplex with a Monitor

If lack of coverage is due to the failure of a critical number of components instead of a design flaw, then additional redundancy may increase reliability. Consider a threeplex with a triplicated monitor as shown in figures 4. The monitor observes the output of the components in the threeplex, and performs a failsafe function. This systems will fail safe if a majority of the monitors have not failed. The working components have failure rate $\lambda = 1e-4/\text{hour}$, and the monitor components have failure rate $\alpha = 1e-6/\text{hour}$. The repair rate is $\epsilon = 1/(24 \text{ hours})$.

Figure 4: Threeplex with Triplicated Monitor

For the threeplex with a triplicated monitor, $mttuf = 2.7150 e+7$ hours.

Consider a fourplex with a triplicated monitor as shown in figure 5

Figure 5: Fourplex with Triplicated Monitor

For this system the $mttuf = 2.3376 e+7$ hours, which is less than the threeplex with a monitor ($2.7150 e+7$ hours).

A conjecture is that adding a component to the working group makes it more likely that the monitor will fail before the working group fails. Since the system fails unsafe if the monitor fails before the working group, the attempt to increase reliability by more redundancy yields a smaller mttuf. To test this conjecture, consider a working fourplex with a quintuple monitor, depicted in figure 6.

Figure 6: Fourplex with Quintuple Monitor

The fourplex with quintuple monitor has $mttuf = 3.8707 \times 10^8$, which is an increase in mttuf compared to the previous systems.

A failure rate example

It's possible for some computations to appear contradictory. For instance, it seems reasonable that increasing the failure rate will decrease the mttuf. Consider the threplex in figure 1. With $\lambda = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ /hour, the mttuf is 4.1786×10^7 . The threplex with $\lambda = 1 \times 10^{-2}$ /hour has $mttuf = 3.3904 \times 10^9$

3. MTTUF IN TERMS OF SINGLE CYCLE PARAMETERS

Computing the mttuf for Markov models is straightforward, although possibly tedious. Computing the mttuf for semi-Markov and globally time dependent models can be analytically hard. One method of reducing the burden is to break the computation into two parts. The first part considers the model without the repair transitions, which we will call the single cycle model. For instance, the single cycle model for a threplex with coverage is given in figure 7.

Figure 7: Single Cycle Model of a Threplex with Coverage

The presence of several absorbing states in the model above implies that their mean times must be conditioned. Strictly speaking, the mean time to state 3 is infinite since the system can go to state 4 and never arrive in state 3. Hence, we need the mean arrival time for state 3 given the system goes to state 3. Similarly for state 4.

The conditional mean can be handled by Laplace transforms for Markov models (and other models for which the Laplace can be computed). Suppose $g(t)$ is a density function for an event. It can be defective (its integral is less than one). Its Laplace transform is

$$L[g(t)] = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} g(t) dt \quad (6)$$

The probability of the event is

$$\int_0^{\infty} g(t) dt = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} L[g(t)] \quad (7)$$

Hence, the conditional mean is given by

$$\mu = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{-\{L[g(t)]\}'}{L[g(t)]} \quad (8)$$

Derivation of the single cycle formula for mttuf

For the first part of the computation, the probabilities and conditional mean times for safe failure and unsafe failure are computed. The second part uses the mean time for repair and the formula derived below to compute the mean-time-to-unsafe-failure. The derivation of the formula uses an intermediate result about summing a series. The notation [expression]' is used for the derivative of [expression].

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n-1)a^{n-1} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} na^n = a \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [a^n]' \quad (9)$$

Since a power series can be differentiated term by term,

$$= a \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a^n \right]' = a \left[-1 + \frac{1}{1-a} \right]' = \frac{a}{(1-a)^2} \quad (10)$$

For a single cycle let the probability of fail safe be P_S , the conditional mean time to fail safe be M_S , the conditional mean time to fail unsafe be M_U , and the mean time for repair be M_R . The mean time to unsafe failure is

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(n-1)M_S + (n-1)M_R + M_U] P_S^{n-1} (1-P_S) = (M_S + M_R) \left[\frac{P_S}{(1-P_S)} \right] + M_U \quad (11)$$

In the infinite series, the term in brackets is the mean time to unsafe failure given (n-1) safe failures followed by (n-1) repairs. This is multiplied by the probability of (n-1) safe failures followed by an unsafe failure. The series is summed using equations (9) and (10) above.

Example

We will recompute the mttuf for the first example using the single cycle formula. the complete model is given in figure 1. The single cycle model is depicted above in figure 7. The Laplace transform equations for the model in figure 7 are

$$\begin{aligned} sP_1 - 1 &= -3\lambda P_1 \\ sP_2 &= 3\lambda C P_1 - 2\lambda P_2 \\ sP_3 &= 2\lambda C P_2 \\ sP_4 &= 3\lambda(1-C)P_1 + 2\lambda(1-C)P_2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The Laplace transforms of the (defective) density functions, the negative of their derivatives, the probabilities, and the conditioned means are given in equations (13)-(20)

$$sP_3 = \frac{6\lambda^2 C^2}{(s+3\lambda)(s+2\lambda)} \quad (13)$$

$$sP_4 = \frac{3\lambda(1-C)}{(s+3\lambda)} + \frac{6\lambda^2 C(1-C)}{(s+3\lambda)(s+2\lambda)} \quad (14)$$

$$-\left[sP_3 \right]' = 6\lambda^2 C^2 \left[\frac{1}{(s+3\lambda)^2(s+2\lambda)} + \frac{1}{(s+3\lambda)(s+2\lambda)^2} \right] \quad (15)$$

$$-\left[sP_4 \right]' = 3\lambda(1-C) \left[\frac{1}{(s+3\lambda)^2} \right] + 6\lambda^2 C(1-C) \left[\frac{1}{(s+3\lambda)^2(s+2\lambda)} + \frac{1}{(s+3\lambda)(s+2\lambda)^2} \right] \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Prob}\{\text{state 3}\} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} sP_3 = C^2 \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Prob}\{\text{state 4}\} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} sP_4 = 1 - C^2 \quad (18)$$

$$\mu_3 = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{-\left[sP_3 \right]'}{sP_3} = \frac{1}{3\lambda} + \frac{1}{2\lambda} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_4 &= \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{-\left[sP_4 \right]'}{sP_4} \\ &= \frac{1}{1+C} \frac{1}{3\lambda} + \frac{C}{1+C} \left[\frac{1}{3\lambda} + \frac{1}{2\lambda} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

For the model in figure 7, the probability of failing safe is $P_S = C^2$. The mean time to repair is $M_R = 1/\epsilon$. Hence, the single cycle formula gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 MTTUF &= (M_S + M_R) \left[\frac{P_S}{(1-P_S)} \right] + M_U \\
 &= \left(\frac{5}{6\lambda} + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \right) \left(\frac{C^2}{1-C^2} \right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{1+C} \frac{1}{3\lambda} + \frac{C}{1+C} \left[\frac{1}{3\lambda} + \frac{1}{2\lambda} \right] \\
 &= \frac{C^2}{\epsilon(1-C^2)} = \frac{2+3C}{6\lambda(1-C^2)} \quad (21)
 \end{aligned}$$

The simplification of the result for the entire model yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 MTTUF &= -3 \frac{\lambda(2\lambda C^2 - 2\lambda - \epsilon - C\epsilon)}{(6\lambda^2 \epsilon C^2 - 6\lambda^2 \epsilon)} \\
 &\quad + 3 \frac{\lambda(2\lambda \epsilon C^2 - 2\lambda \epsilon)(-6\lambda^2 - 5\lambda \epsilon)}{(6\lambda^2 \epsilon C^2 - 6\lambda^2 \epsilon)^2} \\
 &= \frac{-6\lambda^2(C^2 - 1)}{6\lambda^2 \epsilon(C^2 - 1)} + \frac{3\lambda \epsilon(1-C)}{6\lambda^2 \epsilon(C^2 - 1)} \\
 &\quad + \frac{-6\lambda^3 \epsilon(C^2 - 1)(6\lambda + 5\epsilon)}{36\lambda^4 \epsilon^2(C^2 - 1)} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{\epsilon} - \frac{1}{2\lambda(1+C)} \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{\epsilon(1-C^2)} + \frac{5}{6\lambda(1-C^2)} \\
 &= \frac{C^2}{\epsilon(1-C^2)} + \frac{2+3C}{6\lambda(1-C^2)} \quad (22)
 \end{aligned}$$

The two approaches give the same answer (which is reassuring).

4. A SEMI-MARKOV EXAMPLE

A system consists of a working unit plus a cold spare. When the working unit fails, with probability C it activates the spare and sends a signal that it has failed. Upon receiving the signal, a repair crew is sent to the site where they replace both the failed unit and the operating spare. If the operating spare fails before the repair crew arrives, it can fail safe (probability C) or unsafe (probability $1-C$). If it fails safe, it sends a signal and traffic is either halted or rerouted. The model for this system is given in

figure 8 where $f(t)$ is the failure density function and $h(t)$ the repair density function.

Figure 8: Semi-Markov Model for a System with Coverage, a Cold Spare, and Repair

The single cycle parameters are given in equations (23)-(28).

$$p_1 = \int_0^{\infty} f(t) [1-H(t)] \quad (23)$$

$$p_2 = \int_0^{\infty} h(t) [1-F(t)] \quad (24)$$

$$P\{SF\} = C^2 p_1 + C p_2 \quad (25)$$

$$P\{UF\} = (1-C) + C(1-C) p_1 \quad (26)$$

$$\mu(SF) = \frac{\left\{ C^2 p_1 \left[\frac{\int_0^\infty t C f(t)}{C} + \frac{\int_0^\infty t C f(t) [1-H(t)]}{C p_1} \right] + C p_2 \left[\frac{\int_0^\infty t C f(t)}{C} + \frac{\int_0^\infty t h(t) [1-F(t)]}{p_2} \right] \right\}}{P\{SF\}} \quad (27)$$

$$\mu(UF) = \frac{\left\{ (1-C) \left[\frac{\int_0^\infty t (1-C) f(t)}{(1-C)} \right] + C(1-C) p_1 \left[\frac{\int_0^\infty t C f(t)}{C} + \frac{\int_0^\infty t (1-C) f(t) [1-H(t)]}{(1-C) p_1} \right] \right\}}{P\{UF\}} \quad (28)$$

Suppose component failure is a normal distribution with mean = 0.5 years and standard deviation = 0.1 years. Suppose repair is normal with mean = 0.02 years and standard deviation = 0.01 years. Then all the above plus the formula in section three yields mtuf = 5.18 years for the semi_Markov model in figure 8.

5. GLOBAL TIME VARYING EXAMPLE

There are two operating units with failure densities $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ where $f(t)=g(t)$. When the first unit fails there is a probability C that it is detected and repair initiated. Repair has density function $h(t)$, which is a semi-Markov transition—time to repair depends on the time since failure, not global time. If the first unit has a detected failure, then there is a probability C that the system fails safe when the second unit fails. If the first unit fails undetected, then the system fails unsafe upon the failure of the second unit because it is not known that one of the units has already failed. The single cycle model is given in figure 9.

Figure 9: System with Maintenance on Demand

The difficult part of this model is that the transitions out of states 2,3,4,and 5 depend upon the time of entry into those states (global time dependence).

Using $f(t)=g(t)$, the probabilities with respect to repair are given in equations (29)-(31)

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_1 &= \int_0^{\infty} f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)] \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} g(t_1) [1 - F(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{f(t_2)}{[1 - F(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)] \quad (29)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_2 &= \int_0^{\infty} f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} h(t_2 - t_1) \frac{[1 - G(t_2)]}{[1 - G(t_1)]} \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} g(t_1) [1 - F(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} h(t_2 - t_1) \frac{[1 - F(t_2)]}{[1 - F(t_1)]} \quad (30)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $p_1 + p_2 = 1/2$ (31)

Using $f(t)=g(t)$ and the symmetry of the model in figure 7 gives equations (32)-(36).

$$\begin{aligned}
 P\{UF_1\} &= P\{UF_2\} \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} (1-C) f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} \\
 &+ \int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-C) g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)] \\
 &= \frac{1-C}{2} + C(1-C) p_1 \quad (32)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P\{SF_1\} &= P\{SF_4\} \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{C g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)] \\
 &= C^2 p_1 \quad (33)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P\{SF_2\} &= P\{SF_3\} \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} h(t_2 - t_1) \frac{[1 - G(t_2)]}{[1 - G(t_1)]} \\
 &= C p_2 \quad (34)
 \end{aligned}$$

$P\{UF\} = (1-C) + 2 C(1-C) p_1$ (35)

$P\{SF\} = 2 C^2 p_1 + 2 C p_2$ (36)

The conditional means are given in (37)-(41).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu(UF_1 | UF_1) &= \mu(UF_2 | UF_2) \\
 &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} [(1-C) f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} \frac{t_2 g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} \\
 &\quad + \int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)] \\
 &\quad \int_{t_1}^{\infty} (1-C) \frac{t_2 g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)]]}{p\{UF_1\}} \quad (37)
 \end{aligned}$$

$\mu(UF | UF) = \frac{2\mu(UF_1 | UF_1) P\{UF_1\}}{P\{UF\}}$ (38)

6. SUMMARY

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(SF_1 | SF_1) &= \mu(SF_4 | SF_4) \\ &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)]}{\int_{t_1}^{\infty} C \frac{t_2 g(t_2)}{[1 - G(t_1)]} [1 - H(t_2 - t_1)]} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(SF_2 | SF_2) &= \mu(SF_3 | SF_3) \\ &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} C f(t_1) [1 - G(t_1)]}{\int_{t_1}^{\infty} t_2 h(t_2 - t_1) \frac{[1 - G(t_2)]}{[1 - G(t_1)]}} \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(SF | SF) &= \\ &= \frac{2\mu(SF_1 | SF_1)P\{SF_1\} + 2\mu(SF_2 | SF_2)P\{SF_2\}}{P\{SF\}} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Let the failure density functions be a Weibull with an increasing rate

$$f(t) = g(t) = 2\lambda t e^{-\lambda t^2} \quad (42)$$

where $\lambda = 1/\text{year}$. Let the repair function h have a fixed time of 0.00001 year, and let $C=0.999$.

With these values,

- $P\{SF\} = 0.999$
- $P\{UF\} = 0.001$
- $\mu(SF|SF) = 0.62 \text{ years}$
- $\mu(UF|UF) = 1.14 \text{ years}$

Using formula (11) gives

$$\text{MTTUF} = 620 \text{ years.}$$

Mean time to unsafe failure is a new topic, but it is applicable in many different fields. This paper offers both theoretical and computational extensions to the state of the art. The computation for Markov models has been simplified and now includes system repair time. A formula for mttuf in terms of single cycle parameters makes it possible to examine semi-Markov models and globally time varying models. More remains to be done. In particular, the current results are often the opposite of what we expect. Perhaps some automatic model generation and computation programs will make it possible to construct and compute more realistic models.

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